

D1.7

Transition2BIO Library – 1st version

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D1.7

Transition2BIO Library – 1st version

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Other

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents structure and interfaces of Transition2bio online library, which has the scope to make available in a transparent, readily available, user-friendly and visual-attractive way all the contents, materials and tools identified and collected in T1.2, the awareness, communication and education toolkits developed on T1.3, other exploitable assets like the lessons learnt (T5.4), the “future skills for the bioeconomy” reports (T3.3), and other relevant materials developed by the project.

D1.7 is composed of the following sections:

1. Executive Summary
2. Introduction
3. Structure of Transition2bio Library
4. Interfaces of Transition2bio Library
5. Contents of Transition2bio Library

2. Introduction

Transition2bio Library will be hosted at the subdomain of Transition2bio website “library.transition2bio.eu” and will be monitored with the same web analytics service (Google Analytics) used to monitor Transition2bio website. More specifically, we will track Library traffic and assess useful statistics that will help to optimise the Library, providing insights also to the communication and dissemination strategy.

Relevant statistics that will be monitored are the following:

- Number of visitors;
- Number of unique visitors;
- From which links (referrals) and countries the web traffic comes from;
- Number of downloaded documents

The Library will be developed using HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, PHP and MySQL database and will be presented in a responsive model suitable for all devices, including mobiles.

The objectives of Transition2bio online Library are:

- Make available in a transparent, readily available, user-friendly and visual-attractive way all the contents, materials and tools identified and collected in T1.2 “Collection of contents, tools, databases, platforms and good practices”
- Cluster the collected materials according to three macro categories (Communication, Education, Support) and make them accessible through a selection of filters explained in section 4
- Provide Transition2bio with a valuable asset to increase the online visibility of the project, attracting users with a set of easily accessible bioeconomy-related materials
- Provide support to all WP2, WP3 and WP4 events and activities to be organised, by offering the above-mentioned access to clustered bioeconomy-related materials

3. Structure of Transition2bio Library

Transition2bio online Library will be structured as showed in the image below:

Figure 1 - Structure of Transition2bio Library

The online Library will be displayed in Transition2bio website’s main menu and provided with a homepage called “Materials”, and three sub-sections named Education, Communication and Support.

4. Interfaces of Transition2bio Library

This section presents the front-end design of Transition2bio online Library home page and sub-sections.

Home page

The home page of Transition2bio online library will feature:

- A brief description of the library
- A search box with search filters explained in section 5
- Three clickable images, redirecting to the three sub-sections of the online Library: Communication, Education and Support to Regions and Public Authorities

Figure 2 - Home page of Transition2bio Library

Communication sub-section

The Communication sub-section will feature:

- A brief description of the sub-section
- A search box with search filters explained in section 5
- A preview of available documents belonging to the sub-section, divided into two carrousel: “Download materials related to communication” and “Latest entries”

Support to Regions and Public Authorities sub-section

The Support to Regions and Public Authorities sub-section will feature:

- A brief description of the sub-section
- A search box with search filters explained in section 5
- A preview of available documents belonging to the sub-section, divided into two carrousel: “Download materials related to Support to Regions and Public Authorities” and “Latest entries”

Education sub-section

The Education sub-section will feature:

- A brief description of the sub-section
- A search box with search filters explained in section 5
- A preview of available documents belonging to the sub-section, divided into two carrousel: “Download materials related to education” and “Latest entries”

The front-end design of the three sub-sections will not change from one sub-section to the other, with the exception of Title, featured image, brief description of the sub-section and introductory sentence for the first carrousel of downloadable materials, related to the specific sub-section.

Each carrousel will feature the possibility to “Show more” and “Show less” materials.

Figure 3 provides an example of the overall look of the sub-section “Education”.

transition2bio

[About](#)
[Materials](#)
[News and Events](#)
[Public Results](#)
[Contact](#)

[f](#)
[in](#)
[t](#)

Education

➤ [Back to search](#)

Lorem ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets.

Search the materials

Categories

Any ▼

Content type

Any ▼

Recommender system

Any ▼

Source

Any ▼

Country

Any ▼

Language

Any ▼

Apply search filters

Download materials related to education

Name of the document...

Lorem ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing typesetting

Download
➔

Name of the document...

Lorem ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing typesetting

Download
➔

Name of the document...

Lorem ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing typesetting

Download
➔

Show more ➤

Latest entries

Name of the document...

Lorem ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing typesetting

Download
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Name of the document...

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Figure 3 - Education sub-section

Search Results: detail page

Figure 4 provides an example of the front-end design of search results detail page.

The materials corresponding to the applied search filters, will be displayed in a table comprising the following information: Title; Categories; Content type; Bioeconomy sector; Source; Country; Language.

The Title of each material will be hyperlinked and will redirect to the detail page of the individual document.

Figure 4 - Search results detail page

Downloadable material: detail page

After clicking on the Title of the document, users will be redirected to the detail page of the document, which will feature:

- Title of the document
- Standard image, based on “Content type”
- Brief description of the document
- Widget to download the document
- Widget to be redirected to the list of search results
- Social media share buttons

Figure 5 - Downloadable material: detail page

5. Contents of Transition2bio Library

The initial set of materials available on Transition2bio Library will first stem from T1.2 (for more details, please refer to D1.3). At later stages of the project, the database of materials will be updated and enriched and, with the support of the entire Consortium, relevant materials stemming from (but not limited to) EU initiatives will be added to the Library.

The search filters that users will be able to apply will be the following:

- Key words: search bar based on title of the document
- Categories
 - Awareness raising
 - Bioeconomy education
 - Biomass availability, quality, supply and sustainability
 - Stakeholders engagement and co-creation
 - Standardisation, LCA, labelling and regulatory hurdles
 - Regional potential, bioeconomy strategies and action plan
 - Uptake of RTD results
 - Foresight, market studies and market roadmaps
 - New value chains and business models
 - Open innovation platforms and facilities
 - Industrial roadmaps
- Content type
 - Article
 - Case Study
 - Database or repository
 - Fact Sheet
 - Games
 - Good practice
 - Infographic
 - Multimedia/video
 - Platform
 - Policy Brief
 - Presentation
 - Project deliverable
 - Project progress/final report
 - Publication
 - Recommendation
 - Training material
 - Other
- Bioeconomy sector
 - Cleaning and hygiene, personal care and cosmetics, health and biomedical
 - Textile products, clothing, sports and toys

- Food packaging, disposable products for catering and events
- Biofuels and bioenergy
- Building, construction and restoration, paintings, decorations and furniture
- Nutraceuticals, environmental bioregulation and biological sensors
- Country*
 - Bulgaria
 - China
 - Denmark
 - Estonia
 - Germany
 - Great Britain
 - Greece
 - Finland
 - France
 - Hungary
 - Italy
 - Latvia
 - Lithuania
 - Macedonia
 - the Netherlands
 - Norway
 - Poland
 - Portugal
 - Romania
 - Slovakia
 - Slovenia
 - Spain
 - Sweden
- Language*
 - Bulgarian
 - Chinese
 - Danish
 - Dutch
 - Estonian
 - German
 - Greek
 - English
 - Finnish
 - French
 - Hungarian
 - Italian
 - Latvian
 - Lithuanian
 - Macedonian

- Norwegian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Romanian
- Slovak
- Slovenian
- Spanish
- Swedish

*These filters may vary according to the materials added to the online Library.

Figure 6 - Transition2bio Library search box

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